

Influence of polyurethane surface treatment on basalt reinforced thermosetting epoxy resin matrix composites: mechanical and thermal properties

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Abstract

Basalt fiber is a new high-performance fiber and possesses excellent properties, such as high tensile strength, outstanding chemical stability, non-combustible and so on. So it is frequently applied as the reinforcement of composites. However, because of smooth surface of basalt fiber, the adhesion between basalt fiber and resin is rather poor, which makes an enormous effect on its application. In this paper, four kinds of deposit ratios of polyurethane dispersion (PUD) were used as the surface modification of basalt-cloth, including 0wt%, 0.31wt%, 0.93wt% and 9.09wt%. The mechanical property and fatigue performance of basalt-cloth reinforced thermosetting epoxy resin matrix composites were tested through tensile test, low cycle tensile test. The viscoelasticity of samples was measured by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and the fracture morphologies of samples were observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The property of basalt/epoxy composites were influenced by the PUD surface treatment due to more interfacial resin adhesion amount on basalt fiber, which was observed by SEM. The tensile strength and knee point strength of 9.09wt% type is up the maximum and higher over 40% than untreated type. Another also concluded that 9.09wt% type is more resistance to fatigue than untreated type. In addition, the interface between

basalt fiber and matrix of 9.09wt% type was more viscosity.

1.Introduction

Basalt fiber is a new high-performance fiber appearing in recent years. It is drawn from melted natural basalt rocks through an orifice in the crucible and wound onto a rotating drum continuously at 1250-1350°C [1]. And then during process, it does not produce harmful substances and add any other materials. So it is also called “green fiber” [2]. The chemical composition components of basalt are SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaO, MgO, K₂O, Na₂O, Fe₂O₃ and FeO [3]. Because of these components, it possesses excellent properties. In Table.1, compared glass fiber, it has higher tensile strength and modulus than E-glass fibers. And the highest use temperature is much higher than the other glass fiber. So it is considered as the alternative of glass fiber in some aspects [4,5]. Besides that, it can be used from 200°C to 600°C without any significant loss of mechanical properties [6,7]. In addition, they have high chemical stability and corrosive resistance. Meanwhile, it also has supernal heat stability, non-combustible, electrical insulation property, low moisture absorption, filterability and radio-resistance [8,9]. For these reasons, basalt fibers are frequently applied as the reinforcement of composites, which is widely used in fire protection, environmental protection, vehicle

manufacturing, construction, military, aerospace and aviation industry. This indicates basalt composites get wide applications in military and civil systems [10-12].

As well known, the interface in fiber reinforced composites plays a very important role in determining the mechanical properties of composites. When the composites encounter an external force, poor adhesion cannot function in force transference between fiber and resin. After resin fall apart, the force just transfer along the fiber orientation direction. So the fiber is pulled out and the reinforcing fiber does not have the initial expected effect. In contrast, excellent interfacial connection may provide composites with structural integrity and good load transferring from fibers to matrix. However, due to the smooth appearance, adhesion between basalt fiber and resin is not perfect and makes an enormous influence on properties of basalt composites. In other words, poor interface restrict the wide range of basalt fiber application and development [13,14]. At present, many efforts have been made to improve poor interfacial adhesion. All kinds of surface treatments are often used to create a fiber/matrix interface possessing different characteristics. V.Manikandan et al. found that basalt fibers were soaked in 1N NaOH and 1N H₂SO₄ separately for 24 hours at room temperature. Results exhibited the tensile strength of acid-treated basalt fiber reinforced composites and base-treated basalt composites were greater 24.15% and 11.01% than untreated types. The inter-laminar shear strength of acid-treated and base-treated composites was higher 11.94% and 2.23% than untreated composites. Next, the impact property of acid-treated and base-treated composites was better 17.91% and 9.58% than untreated types. This illustrated that acid and base surface treating agent on basalt fiber improves obviously mechanical properties of composites combing basalt fiber and unsaturated polyester matrix. And also the acid attacked basalt fiber

reinforced composites was superior to base-treated basalt fiber reinforced composites [15]. Binwei et al. suggested that the introduction of inorganic nano-SiO₂ particles could improve the surface roughness, which could enhance the mechanical combination force between the fibers and resin matrix. The modified nanoparticles were prepared by mixing nano-SiO₂ precursor and 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (KH-550) with a mass ratio 100:3 at 80°C under stirring for 3 hours. After nano-SiO₂ particles surface treatment, the inter-laminar shear strength of basalt reinforced composites increased by 15% compared with the untreated ones [16]. Denni Kurniawan et al. found that after immersed in water-based silane solution for 15min, the tensile strength of the composites combing basalt fiber and polylactic acid were higher 25.72% than untreated types. However, the modulus and elongation did not change a lot. In water-based solution, 0.3%v/v of glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy silane was added [17]. Yuqiu Yang et al. suggested Isocyanate based polyurethane was applied as the surface treatment for cleaned glass fiber reinforced epoxy matrix. The tensile strength of PUD(6.49wt%) treatment on glass fiber reinforcement composites was higher 79.66% than untreated types. Meanwhile, the tensile strain of 6.49wt% type was greater 118.48% than untreated. But the modulus of all types (virgin type, 0.76wt%, 1.51wt% and 6.49wt%) kept the nearly same value compared with non-treat GF/Epoxy. After PUD treatment, the composites owned better interfacial bonding property [18]. From previous studies, the effect of PUD surface modification was better than others. So in this paper, PUD was used as the surface treatment for basalt-cloth. The aim of the present work was to investigate and analyze the mechanical, fatigue, viscoelasticity properties of basalt/epoxy composites after basalt-cloth surface treating by polyurethane.

Table. 1. Mechanical properties of basalt fiber and glass fiber [4,5]

Property	Basalt Fiber	S-Glass Fiber	E-Glass Fiber
Density(g/cm ²)	2.65-3.05	2.46-2.49	2.55-2.62
Tensile strength(MPa)	3000-4840	4590-4830	3100-3800
Modulus(GPa)	79-93	88-91	76-78
Elongation at breaking(%)	3.1	5.6	4.7
The highest use temperature(°C)	650	300	350

2.Materials and Method

2.1 Material

Basalt-cloth with a textile structure of twill was used as reinforcement. On the other hand, thermosetting bisphenol-A epoxy (JER828) and amine-system harder (JER-W) were used as the matrix system in a ratio of 100:24, supplied by Mistubishi Chemistry.LTD.

2.2 Surface treatment of basalt-cloth

Before surface treatment, basalt-cloth was washed by acetone and put in the oven drying for 20 minutes in order to clean the auxiliary components on the basalt. Polycarbonate Diol Polyurethane Dispersion (UW-5002) as surface treating agent was provided by UBE Industries Ltd. According to different diluted ratios, PUD was diluted with the distill water for the treatment of basalt woven fabric. Firstly, the original basalt-cloth was weighed as *Mo*. The following step was that the basalt-cloth was submerging into the different PUD solution for 10 seconds, which was diluted with diverse ratio of distill water. And then it was wrapped by a tissue paper and then put into the drying oven at 140°C for an hour to evaporate the redundant water. Finally, the weight of treated basalt-cloth *Mp* was measured again. The PUD contention was calculated by the following equation:

$$Pwt\% = \frac{Mp - Mo}{Mo} \cdot 100\%$$

Where *Mp* corresponded to treated weight of basalt woven after drying in oven, *Mo* corresponded to non-treat weight. In this paper,

0wt% (virgin), 0.31wt%, 0.93wt% and 9.09wt% treatment were designed and carried out. The dilution ratio and pick-up ratio was summarized and provided in Table.2.

Table. 2. Surface treatment dilution ratio

Dilution Ratio PUD:Distilled	Pick-up Ratio %
----	0%
1:7	0.31%
1:3	0.93%
1:0	9.09%

2.3 Fabrication of basalt/epoxy composites

Hand layup and hot press molding technical was used for the preparation of basalt-cloth reinforced thermosetting epoxy resin matrix composites. Firstly, mixed epoxy and harder were put into the vacuum oven for 15 to 20 minutes at 70°C in order to increase the liquidity for better mixing, impregnation and getting rid of the entrapped air-bubble. Afterwards, one layer of treated or non-treat fabric with the size of 250mm×250mm was impregnated into matrix resin within 2-3 minutes to keep the matrix resin’s fluidity. And then impregnated composite sheets were cured by hot press machine with applied force of 170 Newton. After being initially cured at 100°C for 2 hours, molded panels were post-curved at 175°C for 4 hours. The fiber content of composites was provided in Table.3. (However, it was difficult to control PUD pick-up ratio in experimental and also the gap between 0.93% and 9.09% type was too large and needed to be improved in the following step.)

Table.3 Fiber content of composites

PUD pick-up ratio (wt%)	Fiber (wt%)
0	78.8
0.31	83.9
0.93	84.7
9.09	65.3

3.Experimental

3.1 Measurement of composites tensile test

For each type, 5 pieces of specimens with the geometry of 20mm X 200mm (width X length) were tested and the mean value of the data obtained was taken as the measured result (Gauge length is 100mm). And then extensometer was attached on the center of sample in order to obtain comparative accurate strain data. Tensile test was carried out by Electronic Universal Tester (Type WDW-20) at a constant speed of 1mm/min under room temperature (22°C).

3.2 Low cycle fatigue tensile test measurements

In the low cycle fatigue evaluation, the cycle load was calculated and determined by 55% of the maximum breaking strength obtained from the quasi-static tensile test. Additionally, the specimens stopped stretching immediately when the strength reached pre-set cycle value and repeated 30 and 100 cycles. At the last cycle, samples were snapped off. During tensile test, acoustic emission (Model DISP) was continuously monitored the fracture process of composites.

3.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Prepared samples with 6 mm X 30 mm (width X length) were tested and analyzed by DMA (Type DMA2980) under stretch mode. Testing temperature was controlled from 40°C to 250 °C at the heating rate of 3 °C /min and the resonant frequency of 1 HZ. 3 pieces of each kind composite were repeated with 0.1 newton of static force under air atmosphere.

3.4 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The fracture surface of the tested samples was sputtered with gold for electron conductivity before observation. The cross sectional observations of molded sample after tensile test were carried out by using a field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM Type Quanta-200). The observations were focused on matrix fusion, state of resin impregnation, fiber/matrix interfacial interactions, and fracture morphologies to characterize interfacial bonding properties.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Tensile Test

The fractures of sample were shown in Fig.1. And it was interesting to note that the crack generally generated along the warp direction.

(a) The authentic fracture sample

(b) The simulate image of fracture sample

Fig.1 fracture sample

The tensile modulus, knee point strength, tensile strength of non-treat and treated composites were summarized in Table.3. And the tensile stress-strain (S-S) curves were gathered in Fig.2. It was indicated that the PUD surface treatment on basalt woven fabric achieved a considerable improvement in mechanical properties of composites.

Table.4. Mechanical property of untreated and treated BF/Epoxy composites

PUD pick -up ratio (%)	Modulus (GPa)	Knee point Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
0	21.9	34.2	355
0.31	27.8	42.0	399
0.93	33.2	44.0	504
9.09	24.0	49.9	503

Fig.2. Stress-Strain curve of BF/Epoxy composites

As shown in Fig.3, it was easy to find that after PUD surface modifying for basalt-cloth, Young modulus of treated types increased sharply. Compared untreated type, the modulus of 0.93wt% BF/Epoxy composites went from 21.89GPa to 33.15GPa, an increase of 51.4%. However, the modulus of 9.09wt% type dropped dramatically. The main reason was considered to the lower fiber content.

Fig.3. Effect of surface treatment on tensile modulus

Knee point played an important role in processing and using of composites. Because once over this point, plastic deformation took place and when load removed, the material would not return its original dimensions. This meant mechanical property of samples would largely alter. So the improvement of knee point indicated more excellent mechanical property, such as fatigue resistance. The way of determining the knee point was shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4. The definition of knee point

Obviously, from Fig.5&6, it was easy to find the PUD surface modification on basalt woven fabric was shown to produce the greatest increase in knee point strength and tensile strength. The knee point strength of the highest PUD pick-up ratio (9.09wt%) went from 34.17MPa to 49.91MPa, rising over 46.06% contrast to non-treat type. Similarly, an improvement in tensile strength was observed in Fig.6. The tensile strength of 9.09wt% type went up 503MPa and rose 47.6% in contrast to untreated type. But the different was when PUD

pick-up ratio up 0.93%, tensile strength maintained stable state. Furthermore, though lower fiber content of 9.09wt% type, its knee point strength and tensile strength still enhanced a lot.

Fig.5. Effect of surface treatment on knee point strength

Fig.6. Effect of surface treatment on tensile strength

4.2 Low Cycle Test

As shown in Fig.7&Fig.8, the modulus of BF/Epoxy composites decreased obviously between the first cycle and the fifth cycle. And in the following cycles, the tensile modulus did not display an apparent falling trend but maintain basically stable within limits. The modulus of 0.93wt% type was still higher than other types. This meant PUD surface treatment improved the fatigue property of basalt reinforced epoxy composites.

Fig.7. After 30 cycles, modulus of composites

Fig.8. After 100 cycles, modulus of composites

AE counts are generated during dynamic and discontinuous microfracture process in the samples. So it is an effective and global measure to evaluate the rupture of composites.

The evolution of the cumulative number of AE counts during tensile test was shown in Fig.9&10. At the first cycle, the untreated type and 0.93wt% type produced AE counts at the same timing-point approximately. Furthermore, it was easy to find the cumulative AE counts of 0.93wt% type was less and smaller than untreated within a certain period of time. This meant 0.93wt% PUD pick up ratio type produced less crack and fracture than untreated type. In general, the composites, which were treated by PUD, were resistance to fatigue.

Fig.9 Acoustic emission activity for composites at the first cycle

Fig.10 Acoustic emission activity for composites at the 100th cycle

4.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) of composites

Dynamic mechanical analysis was a useful tool to evaluate the viscoelastic behavior of composites. The storage modulus, the loss modulus were measured as a function of temperature, which were plotted in Fig.11~12. In glassy region, the motion energy was not enough to arouse the motion of chain segment. So in this region, the main chain of polymer was in frozen state and the modulus was higher than other state. As temperature increased, the components became more mobile and the modulus decreased a lot.

From Fig.11, it was clearly shown that the storage modulus decreased with adding PUD pick-up ratio on basalt woven in glassy and rubbery region, compared with the untreated type. This indicated the PUD surface treatment given the composites more flexibility. In general, the 0.93wt% PUD treated on basalt-cloth reinforcement composites owned more viscosity of interface and the fatigue property of composites was better. In addition, the reduction from glassy to rubbery region also exhibited tendency with higher PUD pick-up ratio.

Fig.11.Storage modulus curves of composites

The loss modulus is a sensitive indicator of all kinds of molecular motions in interface of composites. The determination of the magnitude of the loss modulus makes it possible to quantify the interface bonding. Strong bonding between fibers and matrix tend to reduce the mobility of the molecular chains at interface and therefore to reduce the loss modulus. In contrast, poor interface bonding should tend to dissipate more energy and therefore the energy loss should be higher [19].

Loss modulus curves of BF/Epoxy composites as function of temperature were presented in Fig.12. It was said that the peak maximum of loss modulus decreased as PUD pick-up ratio increased. The decline in peak height of 0.93wt% type suggested greater hindrance to any large scale motion of polymer chains. In other words, PUD surface treatment improved

the interfacial bonding of basalt fiber and epoxy resin. And this was the main reason contributed to the advance of tensile strength and knee point strength.

Fig.12.Loss modulus curves of composites

4.4 Morphologies of BF/Epoxy composites

tensile fracture

The SEM images in Fig.13 showed the surface morphologies of untreated and 0.39wt%, 0.93wt% and 9.09wt% PUD pick-up ratio treated basalt reinforced composites. It was easy to find after surface treatment, the resin on the fiber become more and the adhesion between fiber and resin is better as PUD pick-up ratio rising. This is the reason lead to the highest knee point strength and tensile strength with 9.09% PUD.

5.Conclusions

In this study, PUD surface treatment on basalt-cloth influenced its reinforced epoxy resin composites obviously. The modulus, the tensile strength and knee point strength, which was obtained from the quasi-static tensile test, improved with increasing PUD pick-up ratio. And at 9.09wt%, the tensile strength and knee point strength were higher over 40% than untreated type and reached the maximum. Furthermore, though lower fiber content of 9.09wt% type, its knee point strength and tensile strength still enhanced a lot. However, the

0.93% type was greater than 9.09wt%. The main reason was considered to the lower fiber content.

In low cycle tensile test, the modulus declined sharply between the first cycle and the fifth cycle. During the following cycle, the modulus maintain basically stable within limits. Besides that, the modulus of 0.93wt% type was still higher than other types. Then the cumulative AE counts of 0.93wt% type was less and smaller than untreated within a certain period of time. This meant 0.93wt% PUD pick up ratio type produced less crack and fracture than untreated type. In general, the composites, which were treated by PUD, were resistance to fatigue.

The more resin adhesion on basalt surface and better interfacial bonding which was observed from SEM illustrated the improvement of mechanical properties of PUD treated composites.

The results from DMA exhibited PUD created a viscosity interface and improved the interfacial bonding between fiber and resin, which made the composites, possess better anti-fatigue property.

Finally, the PUD surface treatment on Basalt/Epoxy composites expended its application because better mechanical property and anti-fatigue property.

(a) Untreated BF/Epoxy

(b) 0.31wt%BF/Epoxy

(c) 0.93wt% BF/Epoxy

(d) 9.09wt% BF/Epoxy

Fig.13 SEM observation of fractured composites

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